

Deliverable 6.1.1

NFDI4ENERGY USE CASE M6.1 DESCRIPTION
03.07.2025

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Published by

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Institute for Automation and Applied Informatics, ROR, Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen

Acknowledgements

The authors of this article have used various preparatory works from the NFDI4Energy to create this portrait, and references have been made where possible. Thanks to all those who are not named. The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. The work was funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – 501865131 within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, www.nfdi.de).

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General Information

Summary

This deliverable showcases a new co-simulation use case created according to the NFDI4Energy Task Area 6 requirements. We started with an analysis of existing scenarios in the KIT Energy Lab. None met all of our requirements, therefore, we designed a new use case to support more complex simulation scenarios based on the existing software and hardware resources at the Energy Lab. The new use case integrates a Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) target, a building model, and a Power-Hardware-In-the-Loop (PHiL) system. We will connect the different components with VILLASnode. In this deliverable, we describe the new co-simulation use case from three different layers: the Energy Research Layer, the Research Enhancement Layer, and the Meta Research Layer that demonstrates the specific role of Research Data Management (RDM) tools and services in co-simulation and energy research domain.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Task Area 6 includes a collection of several use cases that are intended to demonstrate how energy research can be enhanced using RDM services. This deliverable describes this for the use case of M6.1. It contains a co-simulation including PHiL that shall be executed with FAIR data and demonstrate the use of the Co-Simulation Ontology developed within Task Area 5. Overall, it shall showcase the capabilities to make co-simulation easier to start with and provide a standardized way to describe co-simulations among different simulation frameworks. Moreover, all data publications shall use the metadata recommendations from Measure 4.3. The use case will be a public tutorial for everybody to get started using NFDI4Energy services.

Energy Lab¹

The energy transition creates many challenges for the operation of energy grids. This provides a large demand for experiments and research. For example, new equipment should be tested in realistic environments before it can be installed in the real grid. Hardware testing in real power grids is hard, because they are critical infrastructure and representative testing environments are extremely rare. The Energy Lab at KIT is the largest research infrastructure for renewable energy in Europe and provides such a rare environment for power system testing. The first NFDI4Energy use case will be created and executed in this laboratory, as it is the ideal playground not only for cutting-edge energy research, but also for how to push the limits of FAIR data and RDM in the energy domain.

The use case shall benefit from the services and hardware available at the Energy Lab to create a representative example for future energy research. Therefore, the general availability and familiarity of the researchers with all of them have had a large impact on the creation of the use case described within this deliverable. The following sections give a quick overview of the equipment and services at the Energy Lab that are relevant in this context.

Experimental Hardware

The Energy Lab incorporates many different hardware components, including renewable energy sources, storage systems, and power-to-X applications. Relevant for the use case described in this deliverable is a controllable resistive load that can be integrated into a real power grid setup and then change its load behavior on demand. It gives the co-simulation the capability to fetch a highly detailed behavior of a sudden load change, overcoming the simplification issues of load model creation.

RTDS

The Real Time Simulator from RTDS Technologies is a state-of-the-art real-time simulator for energy grids. It uses purpose-built simulation hardware to easily interact with digital and analog external signals, making it ideal for any kind of PHiL simulations. The hardware is structured as a server rack that can contain a flexible amount of computing cores and interface cards. It is possible to connect multiple racks together to increase computing power. The simulation uses a high time resolution with a single time step consisting only of a few microseconds. This enables analyzing electromagnetic transients (EMT) during grid operation. This is especially important for investigating switch on/off events of generators, consumers, and switches. The Energy Lab provides two RTDS NovaCor racks that we will use to perform the described use case.

VILLASFramework

VILLASFramework (VILLAS) is a collection of loosely coupled components to enable Geographically Distributed Real-time Simulation (GD-RTS) and Power-Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHiL) experiments. VILLASnode is a communication gateway and a protocol translator. It enables the actual communication between the components of the experiment. Remote equipment can be controlled with VILLAScontroller. It is able to configure, start and stop simulation components. VILLASweb provides a central control platform with a dashboard to visualize the experiment values during simulation. Communication in Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) experiments needs to meet hard real-time requirements. With VILLASfpga VILLAS offers a way to connect Xilinx FPGAs with VILLASnode. These FPGAs can create a physical link to HiL components, providing predictable and low latency communication. VILLAS has previously been used at the Energy Lab to perform PHiL simulations. The domain experts at the lab are already familiar with it and it is possible to rely on previous examples to build up the use case. In addition, the VILLAS development team from the RWTH Aachen is directly involved in this use case. They will extend the framework during the course of the project and host parts of the use case on their own infrastructure.

¹<https://elab.kit.edu/>

Functional mockup units (FMU)

FMUs are bundled standalone simulation components that follow the Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) specification. They can be embedded in various co-simulation setups. They are packed inside a ZIP archive and contain a dynamically linked library to be used in a simulation. The necessary data interfaces of the library are specified in an XML document. In it users can describe all available data output streams and all necessary data input streams. For the presented use case integrating them will make the simulation more heterogeneous and open up a variety of components that could be integrated in future simulations, as FMUs are broadly used throughout different domains and are not just limited to power systems.

Use Case Description

Co-Simulation is a topic that has attracted many publications throughout the last years, especially if it includes Power-Hardware-In-the-Loop in laboratories like the Energy Lab. It makes it possible to test new algorithms or hardware in a controlled environment. This is very hard to do in a real power grid, as every error that might occur directly affects the power supply of consumers, causing financial losses to the operating company. Moreover, co-simulations are more complicated if they include heterogeneous components using different communication channels and protocols. As heterogeneous Co-Simulations, including PHiL, are one of the core competencies of the Energy Lab the presented NFDI4Energy use case will also focus on this area of research.

Search for applicable use cases at KIT Energy Lab

We collected a list of requirements that represent the interests of NFDI4Energy for a representative use case to find similar, already existing co-simulation scenarios at the Energy Lab.

The following requirements were used to identify suitable scenarios for the use case:

1. Use VILLASframework
2. Combine heterogeneous simulators that require non standardized coupling methods
3. Include at least one hardware component
4. Used co-simulation models should be available using an open license

It was important to find existing energy domain simulation scenarios at the EnergyLab, to help create the NFDI4Energy use case, as the involved team of NFDI4Energy are not dedicated energy researchers but computer scientists.

We selected VILLASnode as a requirement because it is already used at the Energy Lab, and the maintainers of the framework from RWTH are involved in this use case. Convincing domain experts to use a different co-simulation framework would likely have failed anyway, so it was important to stick to an existing solution.

Moreover, the coupled components shall not just rely on already existing coupling methods, so the flexibility of the use case can be demonstrated. This of course means that any previous simulation scenario must be extended to contain something new, but that is much easier than to create an entire scenario from scratch.

The use of existing hardware from the Energy Lab for HiL will produce more accurate simulation results, as all models are evidently just a partial representation of the real world. Moreover, the purchase and maintenance of hardware can economically only be justified if it is used frequently.

If the co-simulation models are closed source and not published anywhere, the previous authors can not be forced to publish it to be used within the use case. Although it is not a hard criterion for the use case that all used models must be publicly available, it is in the interest of NFDI4Energy to promote the publication of co-simulation models.

So, with all those requirements in mind, a search of existing simulation scenarios was conducted at the Energy Lab. The results are presented in the next section.

Local energy communities

In [1], the authors present a co-simulation scenario for Local Energy Communities (LECs), where two geographically separated laboratories at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ) and Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) are connected through the VILLASframework. As shown in Figure 1, the campuses of the two research centers are considered as LECs. RTDSs are used at KIT to simulate the campus grid and most of the transmission grid. The KIT grid model is simulated in real-time on the first RTDS Novacor with a time step of $50 \mu s$, which allows the EMT simulation of the KIT grid. On FZJ side an Opal-RT simulator is used for the simulation of the campus that is coupled to another RTDS that simulates the remaining part of the transmission grid. VILLAS provides a link between all three RTDS instances that are distributed on the two locations. For the use as NFDI4Energy use case it still has some disadvantages: The co-simulation scenario presented in the paper only couples one type of simulator (RTDS) and does not consider HiL. Secondly, the simulation models used by the different research centers are closed-source, and each model has its own unique structure, which increases the complexity of the use case.

Figure 1: Co-simulation of Local Energy Communities.

Power-Hardware-In-the-Loop (PHiL) grid coupling strategies

The second co-simulation scenario [2] is a digital framework for local and geographically distributed simulation of the power grid in the Energy Lab. It covers multiple attempts of grid couplings sometimes with and sometimes without hardware. The most relevant case is shown in Figure 2. There, VILLASnode couples two RTDSs targets to create a distributed real-time simulation. One of the RTDS targets is connected to a hardware test device through an Opal-RT PHiL setup. This setup enables the simulation of EMT. Compared to the previous simulation scenario, this scenario fulfills the requirements for HiL experiments. However, this scenario still has some similar limitations to the first scenario, for example, co-simulation with VILLASnode is only done between two RTDSs and the grid model is closed source.

Figure 2: Co-simulation of Two RTDS and OPAL-RT to Connect HiL.

Lab coupling framework

The last existing solution that we could find is not a simulation scenario, but rather a framework for integrating hardware from other remote laboratories via VILLASnode. This framework provides a service that allows hardware from different laboratories to be easily integrated into the simulation. In addition, VILLASnode has been installed on dedicated real-time operating systems to better support high network latency. Network delays can significantly affect the synchronization and accuracy of simulations when connecting remote laboratories. While the infrastructure is useful in general, it

does not directly provide a starting point for the NFDI4Energy use case and another co-simulation scenario needs to be found.

Concept of use case in NFDI4Energy

A use case in NFDI4Energy is intended to demonstrate how research can be done differently and profitably by using RDM tools and services. It usually consists of three layers: traditional energy domain research, enhancements in processes and data FAIRness and a meta research layer.

The first can be any feasible energy domain research question using a suitable method.

The second layer focuses on the actual implementation of RDM tools and services within the traditional energy domain research, so it becomes enhanced. This often aligns with the FAIR principles, and is focusing on the data and the method applied, to improve research for oneself and others that might benefit from previous work.

The meta layer focuses on an explicit search for and description of pain points and challenges in existing research that could be overcome with new additions to the research enhancement layer. Of course, the meta layer helps to identify challenges through the use cases themselves but it requires certain NFDI4Energy services and tools as new research enhancements to actually make a difference. So this layer might also include the search for or implementation of new RDM tools and services. All of these steps form the basis for what shall be demonstrated with an NFDI4Energy use case.

This can be considered from the process steps of the RDM data life cycle. The life cycle contains six steps: Planning, Production, Analysis, Storage, Access, and Re-Use. For each step NFDI4Energy provides different services and tools. So, a use case is effectively used to demonstrate the application of the services and tools to improve conventional energy research.

Use Case Overview

Since the existing co-simulation scenarios that have been found at the Energy Lab do not meet all requirements of NFDI4Energy, a new use case needed to be created. The new use case is shown in Figure 3. It encapsulates several co-simulation components that are connected via VILLASnode. It includes the existing parts like the VILLAS infrastructure and the PHiL example with the R-load, which then already satisfies requirements 1 and 3.

New components include the actual grid model for RTDS, which needs to use an open license to satisfy requirement 4. For requirement 2 it is necessary to include heterogeneous components, which shall be achieved by including a building model that is developed in Modelica and then exported as a Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU), as well as the inclusion of an InfluxDB that provides Photovoltaic (PV) production time-series from real-world measurements.

Figure 3: New use case

Energy Research Layer

The research question that the use case shall address on the Energy Research Layer is to analyze the effect of controllable low-voltage transformers on distribution grids with car charging infrastructure. Effectively analyze the voltage stability in distribution grids once large loads like electric car chargers are connected. Connecting a load that is drawing high power, can also be represented by the connection of a low resistance load. This means the voltage of the entire low voltage grid will drop. Theoretically, a controllable transformer should be able to counteract the voltage drop. This should be verified with the previously mentioned heterogeneous co-simulation using VILLASnode. A large load increase in the low voltage grid shall be introduced to the simulation by a real hardware device (R-load). An additional goal is the integration of a spatially distributed dashboard component into the simulation, to have remote observability of the voltage stability in the experiment. For this purpose, the voltage at multiple locations within the low-voltage grid shall be measured and visualized. Additionally, it could be possible not to use a predefined time to trigger a load increase, but to do it via a user signal from the dashboard.

The low voltage grid is based on the IEEE European Low Voltage Feeder model^[3]² and is simulated using the RTDS hardware at the Energy Lab. The feeder is structured as a star layout that is supplied by a single transformer. Some of the loads of the original feeder case are replaced with the custom co-simulation components.

Most importantly, the large load is integrated via the necessary PHIL components using an Opal-RT co-simulator. The load can be controlled via signals from the RTDS simulation of the LV grid. This is utilized to suddenly increase the load power of the hardware device at a given point in time during the simulation.

Another replaced load is used for the time-series data from the historical database that represents a large building with a PV and battery system and its respective energy infeed and consumption profile. This will be utilized using the capabilities of VILLASnode to directly communicate with a time series database, therefore effectively providing some degree of volatility to the simulation.

Moreover, a thermal and electric coupled building model that is wrapped into a FMU is integrated into the co-simulation to provide variable power consumption, also based on historical data and the configuration of the model.

VILLASnode supports the coupling of different simulators using so-called "node" types. Each node type implements a specific communication channel and/or protocol.

For the presented use case it is required to couple an RTDS, an Opal-RT, an Influx database and a FMU together. By default VILLAS does already support all but the FMU interface. Some of the implementation details for integrating an FMU into a VILLAS simulation can be found in a later subsection.

Overall the coupling will integrate the different components with different update frequencies. The RTDS simulation will run on a high timely resolution compared to the other components, so the behavior of the grid can be analyzed in higher detail than the behavior of each coupled simulation component. For the sake of showcasing the FAIR and Meta Layers of the NFDI4Energy use case this is not a problem.

Considering the research data life cycle this traditional energy research does focus especially on the *Planning*, *Production*, and *Analysis* phases, as described by the research question and technical components that are necessary to achieve the goal. However, NFDI4Energy wants to showcase new services that can improve research, so the next section will cover improvements in regard to the FAIR principles.

Meta Research Layer

Throughout the RDM life cycle many challenges and improvement potentials can be identified for the presented use case.

²<https://cmt.ee.ieee.org/pes-testfeeders/resources/>

Starting of in the *Planning* phase, one mayor challenge is the fact, that although it is intended to do a data publication and long-term storage of data, it is often delayed and attempted to be done at the end of the project. This usually causes time conflicts with the last content steps and is therefore not finished. Moreover, the search for existing models or data sets that can be helpful is usually challenging due to the limited amount of available resources, the lack of appropriate data platforms and bad metadata.

In the *Production* phase, a core issue is the high complexity of the co-simulation setup and modeling which makes it extremely hard to reuse components and models from other people as just understanding them takes a long time. Also it is not really possible to transfer an idea from one co-simulation framework to another, as both concepts and terminology are heavily different between the frameworks.

During the *Analysis* phase, it is hard to compare results to any other online publications, as it is mostly not possible to reproduce an experiment from another research group.

The *Storage* phase brings up the topic of target storage system selection and the respective metadata creation. It is not always clear what platform to store the data on, and what proper metadata annotations are.

For the *Access* phase, it is important that a published data set or co-simulation model can be found by others. This only works if the platform provides good indexing and a proper metadata record of each of the stored data sets.

At last, within the *Re-Use* phase it must be possible to actually work with available co-simulation models. This is again very challenging due to the many different frameworks and modeling systems that require a large amount of knowledge to get a model to work.

The following subsection will explain the enhancements that the described use case will follow to tackle the above challenges.

Research Enhancement Layer

One important topic to improve research over the last couple of years has been the goal to make research and its data FAIR. The FAIR principles refer to the terms Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. They provide a guideline on data management and ensure that data can be easily processed and shared by both humans and machines [4]. The application of the FAIR principles in co-simulation is becoming more and more important as they support more efficient data sharing and integration between different systems.

All data required for and produced by the co-simulation that is not further restricted by a non-open license, is going to be published in a public data repository. We will also use the DBPedia databus or similar technologies to register the published information in a standardized format, enhancing the findability and interoperability of data. Following the FAIR principles, the simulation artifacts will be annotated with metadata. Metadata is able to provide information about the simulation artifacts, such as environments, parameters used for simulation, version of the simulation model, and so on. Metadata annotation makes it easier for researchers to understand the context and relevance of the data, thereby improving the findability and reusability of simulation results and models. We will rely on the metadata guidelines of NFDI4Energy Measure 4.3 to find the best possible annotation for the simulation artifacts.

These steps will improve research in the RDM data life cycle phases of Storage and Accessibility.

Before most research projects or larger experiments, it is useful to create a Data Management Plan (DMP). NFDI4Energy does provide a service to create a DMP which helps to think through the life cycle of all the data that is required or produced throughout the project. This can lay the foundation to proper data publication even if the time is running low at the end of projects.

In order to better share and further improve the reusability of data of the use case, the co-simulation will be specified using the co-simulation scenario ontology developed in Task Area 5[5]. This ontology allows to consistently define the co-simulation components, their roles within co-simulation, the communication methods, and the data flow between them. Instead of relying on technical implementation details, we use the semantic representations to describe how the system is organized and

how each part interacts with the others. The benefits of this kind of description can be concluded as follows:

- Easier switching to other co-simulation frameworks through standardized descriptions
- More machine-understandable specifications using semantic annotations
- Faster learning curve when different co-simulation scenarios share a common and well-defined ontological language
- Possibility to verify and reproduce results from co-simulations performed by others
- Broader accessibility of co-simulation setups to users with different technical backgrounds

As shown in Figure 4, co-simulation relies on input data and models and generates output data during its execution. The inputs are stored in both a private Energy Lab data storage as well as public data repositories. The output will be stored in a public data repository. Data access and transfer will be done through the private data layer and the public data layer. The semantic co-simulation specification is used to describe the simulation process, model, inputs, outputs, and other elements. Through the overarching metadata search, users can easily find, identify, and reuse existing resources. With this meta-description, experiments can be deployed and executed at different locations as long as they are equipped with similar or identical hardware infrastructure in the laboratory. In addition, we will also use a service in our later research to automate the orchestration and execution of a given co-simulation specification. This will reduce the need for manual configuration and help to improve the interoperability and reusability of the experiments.

The described enhancement steps of the use case help to target Planning life cycle steps with a DMP, assist the data Production step with the use of the semantic co-simulation specification. The latter is further improved by using automated data access patterns as much as possible. The Analysis phase further benefits from the immediate publication of co-simulation outputs as this enables the use of external analysis applications like a scenario comparison of the used data repository. At last the Re-Use of existing published co-simulation specifications shall be simplified in the Simulation-as-a-Service Hub that is being created by Task Area 5.

Figure 4: Semantic linkage and storage in registries for distributed data access.

Technical details of the use case

Along the development and testing of the presented use case many topics will need a closer look in regard to the actual solution used. So far, two topics have been in the focus of large discussions and shall be shared within this deliverable, to give some first insights into the working principles of the co-simulation.

FMU VillasNode integration

At first, we considered implementing a standalone FMU simulator, fully decoupled from VILLAS and using shared memory or network sockets to communicate with it. This approach has been discarded as it would include re-implementing functionality VILLASnode already provides. Instead, we will implement a network socket-based connection between the FMUs and VILLASnode. The final product will be an FMI-based simulator for FMUs that functions as a (pseudo) node type. The software component will include VILLASnode as a library and use the VILLAS-internal implementation of sockets for easy coupling with the rest of VILLASnode.

Until the proper C++ code is implemented and tested we currently use a minimalistic Python implementation that communicates with VILLAS over the Websocket protocol.

Creation of RTDS version of the IEEE European Low Voltage Feeder Model

The choice was made to use the IEEE European Low Voltage Feeder model as a foundation for the co-simulation. This requires an RTDS-executable version of the model. The original files are only available as CSV files which makes it necessary to convert them into an RTDS model. A manual creation of the feeder model in RTDS is too time consuming and error prone, so the creation needs to be attempted via Python scripting.

Research on RTDS model creation in Python yielded two potential solutions: First, the official RTDS Python API of RTDS (`rscadfx`) and secondly, a community project that allows the creation of RTDS files from a Python script [6].

The official project is used to automate a running instance of RSCAD while the community project can work on the files without a running instance after the component files of the installation have been parsed once. While the second one seems to be more straightforward from a workflow perspective, it is not compatible with the RSCAD version 2.4 that is used for this use case. So the official Python package `rscadfx` will be used. However, to properly create an RTDS model it is necessary to know the correct names of each of the components that shall be placed in the simulation, which makes it hard for anyone that is not using RSCAD frequently.

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Glossary

PHiL Power-Hardware-In-the-Loop

HiL Hardware-in-the-Loop

RDM Research Data Management

LECs Local Energy Communities

RTDS Real-Time Digital Simulator

EMT electromagnetic transients

FMU Functional Mock-up Units

FMI Functional Mock-up Interface

PV Photovoltaic

VILLAS VILLASFramework

DMP Data Management Plan